

ANCHORED IN LEGACY, DRIVEN BY PURPOSE: LEADERSHIP NARRATIVES OF MIDDLE ADMINISTRATORS IN SECOND-GENERATION FAMILY-OWNED SCHOOLS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17454764>

ABSTRACT

This qualitative study explored the leadership narratives of middle administrators working in second-generation family-owned schools to understand how they navigate their roles within the intersecting demands of personal, professional, and relational responsibilities. Guided by a narratological lens, ten participants were recruited through purposive sampling and underwent face-to-face in-depth interviews. Thematic and cross-narrative analysis were utilized in the study. Across the narratives, five threads were generated, namely: emotional toll of fulfilling multiple roles as educators, leaders, and family members, leadership identity evolving through immersion, mentorship, and institutional loyalty, complexities of working in a family-owned institution where personal and professional spheres overlap, school's culture of faith and respect shaping character and grounding leadership, and deep sense of belonging nurtured by a caring and supportive work environment. By highlighting these narratives, the findings provided insights to strengthen the leadership development of middle administrators and offer practical implications for the sustainability of second-generation family-owned schools.

Keywords: *Educational leadership, family-owned schools, middle administrators, narratology, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

Educational leadership, the process of guiding and influencing others toward a shared vision (Bush, 2018), is vital in schools, especially through the role of middle administrators. In family-owned schools, these middle administrators work to balance leadership tasks with their responsibilities as educators (Basset & Shaw, 2018) and are key to implementing the founders' vision (Hargreaves & Shirley, 2019). However, second-generation family-owned institutions often face leadership ambiguity due to the overlapping of family intimacy and work responsibilities (Hyslop et al., 2023), which in turn creates tensions that cause difficulties in maintaining professional management (Nandiroh et al., 2023). Understanding the experiences of middle administrators in this context is crucial to balancing family values and legacy with effective school leadership (De Massis et al., 2021).

Worldwide, middle administrators continue to experience a rapidly increasing trend in significant challenges (Nixon, 2023; NASSP, 2022). In Nepal, the study conducted by Upadhyaya and Kuknor (2025) among family-owned schools run by second-generation family owners revealed significant ambiguities in the leadership roles of middle administrators resulting in a feeling of uncertainty in terms of career progression and promotion opportunities. In Australia, Nixon (2023) reported that over half of middle leaders in local schools leave their positions within 12 months, indicating an increasing trend in middle administration leadership instability. Moreover, in the United States of America, findings from the study conducted by the National Association of Secondary School Principals (NASSP, 2022) showed that over 50% of middle administrators in American schools are under significant strain, underscoring the urgent need to address this growing leadership concern. Taken together, these findings reveal a global incidence of middle administrators grappling with complex issues; however, how these issues, navigated within the context of second-generation family-owned schools, remains poorly studied.

In the Philippines, while there is a scarcity of studies focusing specifically on middle administrators working in family-owned schools, related studies provide significant insights into the topic. The study conducted by Perez (2021) among 207 middle managers from 31 higher education institutions in Batangas found that middle administrators face systemic issues within the organization, including role ambiguity and a significant lack of autonomy. Meanwhile, the study of Ramos and Malangen (2023) among 12 middle administrators in a school in Quezon City suggested a significant rise in personal challenges particularly burn-out and work-life balance, professional challenges such as task overload, professional development and hierarchical issues, and relational challenges specifically low morale, organizational trust and empathy. While these studies provide valuable insights into the middle leadership, they are primarily focused on higher education institutions leaving a significant gap in understanding the experiences of middle administrators within the context of second-generation family-owned schools. Further research focusing specifically on second-generation private family-owned schools in

Davao City is crucial to understanding the unique challenges and opportunities related to the leadership experience of middle-level administrators within this context.

Since existing studies are heavily focused on organizational factors (Sihombing & Berlianto, 2017; Dutta & Dhir, 2021), there remains a need for more research that specifically focuses on the leadership experiences of middle administrators in second-generation family-owned institutions. Moreover, the current literature on family-owned schools (Macasinag, 2019) focuses on the family members as owners managing their schools and not on the experiences of the middle administrators. Furthermore, despite the many studies pointing towards the importance of middle leadership in school success (Irvine & Brundrett, 2016; Harris & Jones, 2017; Basset & Shaw, 2018), middle administrators have received little interest when compared to senior leaders (Harris & Jones 2017; Harris et al., 2019; Lipscombe et al., 2023). Through a narratological approach, this study aims to address these gaps by diving into the second-generation family-owned middle administrators' stories, perceptions, and interpretations of their experiences.

Research Questions

1. What personal, professional, and relational challenges do these middle-level administrators encounter in balancing family expectations with institutional responsibilities?
2. How do middle administrators in second-generation family-owned schools describe their lived experiences as educational leaders within a family enterprise?
3. How do their leadership identities evolve within the unique context of a second-generation family-run educational institution?
4. What values, narratives, and motivations shape their purpose and drive as they navigate their roles?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a qualitative research methodology, specifically employing narratology. Qualitative research design is interested in how people interpret their experiences, how they construct their worlds, and the meaning they attribute to their experiences (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016). Clandinin and Connelly (2000) define narratology as a process of comprehending individual experiences through stories, how they are collected and interpreted, and how the co-construction of stories reflects lived experiences. The researcher used narratology to identify the participants' significant life experiences and to investigate the influences of these experiences on their leadership journey in second-generation family-owned institutions. Creswell and Poth (2018) posit that narratology allows the researcher to comprehensively explore the lived experiences of the participants and offer insights into how these lived experiences shape their leadership within the context of second-generation family-owned schools. Moreover, the

researcher conducted in-depth interviews (IDIs) as the research technique to extract the individual leadership experiences lived by middle administrators working in second-generation family-owned schools.

The participants in this study were 10 middle administrators selected through purposive sampling. These middle administrators serve as department heads, academic coordinators, or assistant principals, balancing leadership duties with academic responsibilities. Their role places them at a unique intersection of policy implementation and daily school operations, making them ideal sources of insight into the dynamics of educational leadership in family-run institutions. The researcher screened their personal details, ensuring they meet the criteria of being currently employed full-time, have served at least eight consecutive years, and are actively involved in both administrative and academic functions within a family-owned school currently managed by the second generation. In terms of vulnerability, although the participants are not considered part of a vulnerable population as defined by ethical research standards such as those belonging to marginalized groups, minors or persons with disabilities, there is a chance for exposure to potential institutional risks. These institutional risks may arise from the unique hierarchical power present in family-owned institutions and the power dynamics present within, particularly when discussing sensitive topics like leadership ambiguity, unclear leadership boundaries or family involvement. To mitigate these potential risks, the researcher clearly informed the participants of the study's scope and its voluntary nature, while their identities will be strictly kept confidential through anonymity in the use of pseudonyms. To ensure justice and transparency, the participants were assured of their right to withdraw at any point during the study should they feel uncomfortable proceeding, without any consequence or obligation to explain. To ensure confidentiality, the researcher used ten participant pseudonyms using symbolic codes from basic supplies found in the school to showcase how middle administrators are essential to everyday school operations in the same way school supplies are vital in the daily tasks within the school.

This research used the method of narrative research designed by Clandinin and Connelly (2000) following a five-step interconnected process for data analysis: narrative immersion, narrative structuring, thematic narrative analysis, inter-narrative comparison, and story reconstruction and interpretation. The researcher spent a good amount of time with the participants to properly gather their stories from a variety of types of information, after which the researcher carefully and meticulously documented each response after thorough transcription. Subsequently, information about the context of these stories was collected. Through this deep narrative immersion, the researcher was able to familiarize herself with the participants' narratives, including their personal logic, emotional perspective, and the meanings their narratives bear in between their lines as reflected by Riessman (2008) that narrative immersion should involve "listening between the lines to capture the meaning beyond words". The researcher began data analysis, which involved reading and re-reading the transcripts. The researcher performed narrative structuring where she arranged the participants' narratives chronologically to form a coherent story to reveal the significant events, major turning points, and the voice of the storyteller embedded in the narratives (Knight, 2009). Through structural analysis, essential

meanings were drawn from the stories relevant to how the participants relayed their narratives (Riessman, 2005). Then the researcher studied the narratives to identify recurring themes across stories. Braun and Clark (2006) define thematic analysis as the process of systematically coding data to find patterns of meaning. Next, the researcher performed inter-narrative comparison to deepen the analysis, where the researcher carefully examined how each participants' narratives relate, contradict, compare or reinforce the narratives of the others (Wertz et al., 2011). Lastly, the researcher conducted story reconstruction and interpretation. This step in the process involved reconstructing the participants' stories following Clandinin and Connelly (2000), where deeper meanings were revealed through the re-construction of the participants' stories.

RESULTS

The cross-narrative analysis of this study revealed the shared threads across the lived experiences of middle administrators serving in second-generation family-owned schools. While each participant brought a unique personal and professional journey, their stories revealed converging themes that illuminate the complex interplay between legacy, leadership, and loyalty. These narratives, woven through varying lenses of blood relation, professional alignment, and institutional stewardship, underscore how leadership identities are shaped, contested, and affirmed within the layered context of family-run educational enterprises. The cross-cutting themes highlight not only the challenges of balancing familial expectations with organizational responsibilities but also the deep sense of purpose and evolving leadership that emerges when personal conviction meets institutional mission.

Profile of the Participants

The participants of the study were 10 middle administrators working for at least eight consecutive years in two campuses of one second-generation family-owned school. All 10 of them participated in the in-depth interview. These participants are a combination of seven females and 3 males, with ages that range from 32 to 44 years old.

Table 1
Profile of the Participants

Pseudonym	Age	Gender	Years in Service	Educational Background
Compass	40	F	21	Master's- Education
Crayon	43	F	14	Bachelor - IT
Cutter	39	M	13	Master's- Education
Eraser	32	F	9	Master's- Education
Fastener	34	M	8	Master's- Education
Glue	41	F	20	Master's- Education
Marker	36	F	15	Master's- Education
Notebook	38	M	15	Bachelor- Education

Ruler	44	F	13	Bachelor- Education
Sharpener	42	F	15	Master's- Education

Through cross-narrative analysis, recurring themes, tensions, and transformative insights emerged, highlighting the shared struggles, values, and evolving identities that characterize their leadership journeys within a family-run educational institution. Shown in Table 2 are the narrative threads that capture these interconnected voices and illuminate the deeper meanings they construct from their roles and relationships.

Table 2
Cross-narrative

Narrative Thread	Key Similarities in Stories	Participants
Emotional toll of fulfilling multiple roles as educators, leaders, and family members	Participants described exhaustion, guilt, stress, and the emotional strain of balancing school leadership, teaching, and familial duties	Compass, Sharpener, Crayon, Notebook, Cutter, Ruler
Leadership identity evolved through immersion, mentorship, and institutional loyalty	Leadership journeys were influenced by role modeling, gradual immersion in responsibilities, and a deepening sense of mission aligned with school values	Crayon, Fastener, Cutter, Glue, Marker
Complexities of working in a family-owned institution where personal and professional spheres overlap	Tensions emerged in navigating authority, relational expectations, and blurred boundaries between personal relationships and professional roles.	Eraser, Cutter, Crayon, Compass
School's culture of faith and respect shaped their character and grounded their leadership	Formation in prayer, spiritual integration, respect for individual dignity, and Christ-centered values were cited as essential in shaping personal and professional identity	Cutter, Eraser, Crayon, Compass, Sharpener
Deep sense of belonging nurtured by a caring and supportive work environment	Participants highlighted affirming relationships, shared values, team spirit, and emotional support from colleagues and superiors	Eraser, Glue, Crayon, Fastener, Compass, Marker, Notebook

Emotional toll of fulfilling multiple roles as educators, leaders, and family members

For the middle administrators in second-generation family-owned schools, leadership is not neatly contained within the hours between the morning bell and the afternoon dismissal. It travels with them into their homes, onto the dinner table, and into the quiet moments they try to reserve for themselves and their families. The overlap of professional responsibilities and personal roles, being a leader, educator, parent, spouse, child, and even a student, creates a constant negotiation of priorities. This is not simply a matter of time management. It is an ongoing emotional balancing act in which the cost is

often measured in missed milestones, lingering guilt, and the physical weariness of being pulled in multiple directions.

For Compass, this collision of roles was felt in the most ordinary of routines, her parental duties that should have been simple, such as checking her children's assignment notebooks. Yet, the demands of school leadership often crowded out these moments, leaving her painfully aware of what was slipping through the cracks. She explains:

So even *ilang mga* assignments, *dili nako matan-aw ... dili nako ma follow up.*
L#38-L#45

So even with their assignments... I can not follow up.

Sharpener experienced a similar drain, though hers was felt most keenly in her marriage and her relationship with her husband. After a day of teaching, administrative work, and pursuing graduate studies, she found herself arriving home with nothing left to give emotionally and physically. She recounts:

If he wants to have time with me, I'm not in the mood anymore because I am already tired. It's really difficult.
L#51-L#52

For Crayon, the challenge was frequently accompanied by guilt. When the balance overwhelmingly tips too far toward work, she felt the weight of what her family was missing. She expounds:

Ma-guilty na ako kasi work-work nalang, I don't have time anymore for my family.
L#78-L#79

I feel guilty because I always just work. I don't have time anymore for my family.

Notebook recalled how this tug-of-war played out during family moments that should have been purely celebratory. Even special occasions like birthdays could be delayed or reshaped around school duties. He admits:

Lisod jud siya. There are times *na* you need to choose your work than your family... for example, birthday *ng anak mo*
L#40-L#41

It is really hard. Sometimes, there are times when you need to choose your work over your family... for example, it is your child's birthday

For Cutter, the emotional cost was most evident in moments of family crisis. He recounted how, during a critical time at work where he had to go on overtime to finish a

project for the school, his mother's sudden health crisis went unnoticed until it was too late. He recalls:

I was actually at work. I was very busy... I didn't know that my mom was already in a coma that time.

L#114-L#115

Others, like Ruler, spoke of a persistent pattern where school obligations overshadowed personal milestones, forcing her to choose work over family. Ruler shares:

If there are events in our family... I really have to prioritize the school.

L#61-L#62

The strain was not just in choosing between two important spheres, but in living with the awareness that someone, may it be students, colleagues, or loved ones, might feel the absence. Notebook described the dilemma when his child fell ill. He recounts:

Sometimes *may sakit ang anak mo*, it's either you need to be absent or get someone who will take care of your kids

L#43-L#44

Sometimes, your child is sick. It's either you need to be absent or get someone who will take care of your kids.

The participants also described coping strategies that helped them sustain this balancing act. Crayon leaned on her husband for shared responsibility at home. She expounds:

I do manage actually, because I would ask for help from my husband. For example, if I'm busy here at work, I will tap him.

L#40-L#42

Cutter relied on his family's understanding of his workload, which removed the added pressure of having to justify time spent at work and less for his family. He explains:

My family is really very understanding when it comes to my work. Let's say I don't have the pressure to ... put more time for the family and less for work.

L#110-L#112

Others adapted through what Crayon called "mind management" where she conditions her family, including her children, for the days when she would have to spend more time at work than home. She says:

Mind management.. Like if you know you will be busy that day or that week, you have to talk to your husband...to your children... I'll be busy. Maybe we can take care of our own responsibilities at home.

L#61-L#65

The emotional resilience needed for a life as busy as that of a middle administrator was evident in Cutter's quick recovery after moments of guilt, allowing him to bounce back easily after some emotional turmoil. He says:

There are a lot of times when I feel guilty. It's a blessing that I am also resilient.
L#131-L#132

Even with resilience as a quality, the struggle of balancing multiple roles is unchanging. Crayon makes deliberate space for family like weekends away, shared games, and travel, not as an afterthought, but as an intentional and necessary counterweight. She explains:

We let them understand my workload, then we treat them out. We will play or go running or even just mental games, board games as long as it is family time. We travel also ... To make it up to them.
L#85-L#88

Across these accounts, the emotional toll is not born of neglect, but of the constant necessity to balance multiple roles that matter deeply. These middle administrators live in the in-between, navigating the blurred edges where leadership, family, and obligations meet. Every day requires fresh negotiation between sacrifice and fulfillment, and in that negotiation, they do more than simply endure, they redefine resilience as the art of holding both worlds without letting either fall.

Leadership identity evolved through immersion, mentorship, and institutional loyalty

The leadership of these middle administrators was not inherited in the job title alone. It was cultivated in the slow living out of experiences, in lessons learned from the mentorship of seasoned leaders like the founders, and in the reinforcement of trust that came from being given meaningful responsibilities. The middle administrators did not just automatically step into their leadership positions out of nowhere. They were shaped over the years through immersion in the school's varied responsibilities, mentorship under the first and second generation owners, and loyalty forged in years of service and commitment to the school's vision and mission.

For Crayon, this evolution of leadership took shape through a journey that took her through nearly every department of the school organizational structure. She recalled her journey through the ranks with both pride and a sense of astonishment, recognizing that each movement, both lateral and vertical, had been a training ground for leadership. From teaching computer to balancing accounts, to returning to the classroom, and then to serving in the registrar's office, every step allowed her to truly understand how the institution operated. She recalls:

I started as a Computer teacher then I was moved to the Accounting staff, then back to teacher, then Registrar's staff then *ito na* position *ko* now in the middle admin.
L#189-L190

Did you know that I was able to work all departments here? I started as a Computer teacher then I was moved to the Accounting staff, then back to teacher, then Registrar's staff then this is now my position in the middle admin.

For Fastener, leadership identity was less about navigating multiple departments and more about being entrusted early on with responsibilities that signaled the owning family's confidence in him. The steady and continuous progression of promotions became professional milestones in a journey defined by mutual trust where each new role was not simply an opportunity to progress up a ladder; rather, it was an affirmation that the school saw him as someone capable of taking on more responsibilities. Being entrusted with leadership positions reinforced his connection to the institution and deepened his sense of accountability. He linked his identity to the trust placed in him by the owners, a trust he felt compelled to honor through his work. He recalls:

Year after year, I got promoted. I learned that nothing is difficult if you are willing to learn the job that's given to you.
L#208-L#211

Similarly, Cutter carried with him the personal mentorship of the school's founders, whose hands-on guidance shaped his vision of leadership, especially at the beginning of his leadership journey. Reflecting on his early years, Cutter shares:

When I started, the original founders of this school were very hands on.
L#196-L#198

For Glue, mentorship evolved in a circular arc where what she once received, from the founders who mentored her, she now gives back to the teachers she mentors under her. When faced with challenges with the people she leads, rather than giving a quick reprimand, Glue goes back to her experience with the founders where she was shaped with understanding, care, patience, and mentorship.

Whenever one of my people is not able to meet the expectations. Instead of just getting mad right away, there is personal coaching that I do... because that's how I learned to be a leader from the first-generation owners.
L#320-L#325

This same pattern of modelling and mentorship is echoed in Marker's experience in the school, underscoring how leadership is mirrored instead of invented. She speaks of the strength of influence passed down from the first to the second generation down to the middle leaders, including herself. She shares:

The first generation influenced me a lot... so we try also our very best to mirror that to the people under us.
L#294–L#297

For Crayon, her life was formed slowly over the years she has spent in the institution, sharing how the school and its owners have been witnesses and participants in her life's milestones. She shares:

Then when I had my son, when I got pregnant, I was already working here and now that son is already in high school. So when I look at my life here, *parang dito na nabuo yung buhay ko. Parang* my whole life, all the big milestones of my life, I spent them all here in the school. That is important to me. I appreciate it.
L#228-L#235

Then when I had my son, when I got pregnant, I was already working here and now that son is already in high school. So when I look at my life here, it's like this is where my life was formed. Like my whole life, all the big milestones of my life, I spent them all here in the school. That is important to me. I appreciate it.

In this close-proximity model of leadership, lessons were not merely taught but demonstrated. The lessons are embedded in the middle administrators' day-to-day decisions, in the way they support their teachers, and in how they nurture their students. This early influence became a reference point for how they would later navigate their own leadership challenges. These narratives reveal that, in this second-generation family-owned school, leadership identity is not formed right at the moment of promotion. It emerges over years of participation, built from the constant interplay of immersion, trust, and mentorship. It is forged in the fluid movement between roles, in the steady accrual of responsibilities that stretch one's capacities, and in the enduring relationships with those who model what leadership should look like.

Complexities of working in a family-owned institution where personal and professional spheres overlap

In a second-generation family-owned school, leadership unfolds in a space where limited authority and familial relations, compounded with relational and professional conflicts, are deeply intertwined. Professional duties are rarely separate from family dynamics, where authority is bounded not only by job descriptions, but also by the presence of owners whose decisions eventually prevail. Though the middle administrators carry the major responsibility for curriculum, programs, teachers, and daily operations, yet their capacity to make decisions is constrained by family approvals, loyalties, and generational hierarchies. Within this complex environment, conflicts among members of the owning make tiny ripples across the institution, making the leadership of middle administrators as much about diplomacy and negotiation as about school management and policy implementation.

Decision-making is rarely a matter of pure policy or procedure. Instead, it is shaped by family hierarchies, personal bonds, and generational dynamics. For middle administrators, this reality creates an environment that is both intimate and intricate, where their every choice must account what is best for the institution, while also respecting the sensitivities of the owning family's relationships with one another across the two generations. Participants described navigating this complex landscape with care as their roles as middle administrators required an awareness of family dynamics, and the skill to act with both professional decisiveness and familial diplomacy.

These middle administrators carried the full burden of leadership without the full authority to decide. Glue reflected on how even clear, reasonable choices could not move forward until owners gave the signal, at times delaying what could have been a quick resolution to simple school decisions. She reflects:

I really just cannot decide on my own. I have to wait for the decision of the owners.
L#180–L#181

She further explained how this limitation in authority extends even to budget and finances. Proposals had to be presented, then left hanging until all the members of the family agreed, stating that this is an issue unique only to family institutions. Glue admits:

In terms of budget as well, you just have to wait if the family will approve it or not. That is unique only to family-owned schools.
L#236–L#242

Career progression also faced an invisible boundary as key positions are generally awarded to direct family members, while other employees are subject to an invisible promotion ceiling regardless of credentials or qualifications. For the middle administrators, they recognize that their careers might not have the opportunity to fully bloom. Glue explains:

It is hard because you don't get promoted much. Only the family will hold the highest positions.
L#157-L#159

Adding on the limitations on authority are familial relations flowing into the professional operations. Even in ordinary decisions, conflicts between family members complicated the flow of work. Eraser shared how even simple decisions on school operations are complicated by conflicting perspectives among the members of the owning family. She says:

Working under one family, sometimes there's a conflict in decision-making among the first and second generation owners.
L#147-L#150

When disputes arose in operating the school, familial relations tipped the scale to their favor, and professional disagreements are often decided on the pull of kinship, instead of on objective assessment. Compass shares:

If ever there are conflicting decisions, the family will support the decision of their own family member rather than siding with an outsider.

L#174-L#177

Crayon shares how working in a family institution requires her to work under multiple bosses, all of whom are members of the owning family. This dynamic sometimes makes the job harder to manage. Crayon shares:

There are a lot of them so *minsan marami kaming boss*, especially since my work here overlaps across different departments. And each department has its own head who is a family member, so I have to transact with many owners. Sometimes that is hard.

L#157-L#163

There are a lot of them so sometimes you have a lot of bosses, especially since my work here overlaps across different departments. Each department has its own head who is a family member, so I have to transact with many owners. Sometimes that is hard.

In the school's daily operations, tension is rarely hidden. Middle administrators described feeling it in the air, as disagreements at the top spilled visibly downward. Cutter recounts:

There are conflicts, there are tensions. We, the middle administrators, would really feel the tension.

L#221-L#225

Nevertheless, the presence of the founders added a much-needed layer of stability. When tensions and conflicts abound, the founders' words carry a weight that silenced debate, even among the second generation. Compass explains:

So what's good with having the first-generation founders still is when they speak, everybody in the family follows.

L#144-L#145

As leadership is passed to the next generation, the middle administrators noticed shifts in style. The founders' teacher-centered ethos gave way to a stronger business approach, blending old, traditional values with modern efficiency. Crayon expounds:

Now that the second generation is here, there is a business side to the school already.

L#177-L#178

These narratives reveal how working in a family-owned school is made complex by the intersecting challenges of limited authority, familial relations, and relational conflicts. For Glue, the challenge lay in accepting that authority was always conditional, as even sound decisions and budget proposals required owner approval. For Crayon, it was recognizing the ceiling of advancement, where the highest positions were reserved for family, regardless of competence. For Compass, it was witnessing how kinship often outweighed fairness, with family members siding with their own family in times of disputes instead of listening to reason. For Eraser, it was navigating disagreements between generations, where even simple operational choices became tangled in family politics. For Cutter, it was enduring the invisible weight of conflicts that rippled through the institution whenever tensions arose among owners. Together, their accounts illustrate that leadership in a family-owned school is not merely about managing programs or people but about negotiating the powerful mix of loyalty, hierarchy, and relational undercurrents that define the institution's life.

School's culture of faith and respect shaped their character and grounded their leadership

Leadership in the school cannot be separated from its moral and spiritual foundations. The participants spoke of faith and respect as core values that continually shaped their identity and way of leading within the institution. What stands out is a school culture where prayer, dignity, and Christ-centered service are lived in everyday work. The stories converge into a narrative where professional life is inseparable from spiritual formation, and where leadership emerges less as a position and more as a vocation grounded in shared faith. The practice of prayer provides the most striking entry point. Sharpener recalled how praying was encouraged not as ritual performance but as sincere conversation before God. She explains:

We are encouraged to make a prayer from your heart.
L#180

Compass extended this culture of prayer into the generational legacy that marked the institution. She remembered vividly how the founders did not only establish rules or schedules in the daily school operations, but they also integrated practices of faith into the life of the school, the teachers, and the students, encouraging them to pray for one another. She recalls:

We always pray for each other. That's how the first generation trained us.
L#242-L#243

For Cutter, this inherited practice of faith and prayer found expression in his own growth. His reflection drew from both the founders and the second generation of leaders, who all embodied values that became his anchor. He expounds:

I think the love for Christ, love for God, that I could really see from the founders of the school where they mold the teachers in Christ-like values. My faith is strengthened here.

L#360-L#368

Yet this culture was not only about prayer and faith; it was also about the assurance of dignity and respect. Eraser described this reality in terms of a safe and principled space she enjoys every day when she enters the school campus. She continues:

There's a feeling of safe space when you are here.

L#305

Crayon gave this moral framework its clearest articulation by naming the essence of what leadership meant within this culture, a moral embedded in the school's core values. She reflects:

I think leadership is service, that is what the school taught me.

L#215

She shares how she serves in her role with a heart of service, always working with the goal of helping others. She expounds that she constantly reminds herself of this during times of conflict with clients or during busy season in her office, in order to avoid stressing herself out. She explains:

Heart of service *talaga*. Like we are here to help always. So now in my department, I always remind myself to be happy to serve. *Kahit minsan awayin ako ng mga parents, or maraming mga urgent na trabaho*, I always work happily *para walang* stress.

L#217-L#219

Heart of service really. Like we are here to help always. So now in my department, I always remind myself to be happy to serve. Although sometimes parents fight with me, or there are many urgent tasks at work, I always work happily so there is no stress.

Taken together, the participants' accounts reveal a leadership culture deeply formed by faith and respect. Sharpener underscored the authenticity of prayer, where leaders are shaped not by scripted words and rituals but by the sincerity of heart. Compass emphasized how the first generation handed down Christ-like habits, embedding prayer and mutual care into the very core of leadership meaning and practice. Cutter drew strength from the example of both generations of owners, seeing in their Christ-centered values a model that continually renewed his own sense of mission and

vocation as a leader and an educator. Eraser highlighted the dignity and safety cultivated in this environment, describing the school as a principled space where one could lead without compromising values. Finally, Crayon tied these threads together by framing leadership itself as an act of service, a daily responsibility to learners, teachers, and colleagues alike.

Deep sense of belonging nurtured by a caring and supportive work environment

For the middle administrators in this second-generation family-owned school, what strengthens their foundation in the institution is not the need for job stability or the prestige that comes with a leadership position. Instead, it stems from the feeling of belongingness, of being part of a community that truly cares and values them. This deep sense of belonging is not a result of a comprehensive human resource program or of structured team building and recollection activities, but it slowly emerges over the years through shared memories and milestones, of shared trauma and heartache, and of the quiet but constant assurance that they are more than just mere employees. When shared faith and mutual respect provide the moral foundation for leadership, belonging is the relational glue that keeps the community intact despite challenges and differences. For the middle administrators, their deepest loyalty to the institution is not contractual nor enforced by binding legalities, but it is forged in the lived experience of being known, remembered, and included in the family.

Crayon shared about how the empathy of her superiors has helped her over the years. She shared that the owning family has rescued her during times of trouble, highlighting that even though the job is difficult, the support of her superiors and colleagues helps her manage. Crayon recounts:

The empathy of my superiors, *maka help talaga siya*. Like *isang tawag lang*, then my boss will come to the rescue. Or like if I have to be absent at work, they will not question me. *Payag lang sila agad*, especially if *may may sakit sa pamilya*, like my kids or my husband. So even if the work is hard, because my workmates and my boss are supportive, *ok lang*.
L#112-L#115

The empathy of my superiors, it really helps. Like with just one phone call, then my boss will come to the rescue. Or like if I have to be absent at work, they will not question me. They will say yes right away, especially if someone is sick in the family, like my kids or my husband. So even if the work is hard, because my workmates and my boss are supportive, it's okay.

Marker reflected on how the demands of middle leadership weigh heavily on her shoulders, and at times threatening to overwhelm her. Yet, what allowed her to endure through the hardships was the culture in the workplace that fostered care and gave her the assurance that she belonged. Within this support network, she did not feel reduced to her workload alone; instead, she was reminded that she could step back, breathe, and tend to herself without fear of judgment whenever necessary, reminding her that she is valued and important. She expressed:

I try to respect myself by trying to manage my time. I have to manage my time. I have to stop, drink coffee or stop chit-chat for a while, or stop to do something that is not relevant to what I've been busy working with.
L#309-L#311

For Compass, this sense of belonging did not grow overnight. It simmered over decades, rising above the absence of blood ties to the owners, and making emotional connections beyond just the workplace. Here, belonging is inseparable from the years spent in close proximity to the same people, watching relationships deepen with time. Even without familial connections, Compass feels that sense of kinship. She explains:

Sometimes, you feel like you are family, you belong together, and you're very close, and you've been together for a long time, like for others, one decade, two decades already.
L#139-L#141

For Crayon, the ties with the school owners had grown so deeply intertwined over the years that personal milestones were shared as naturally as professional ones. Crayon shares:

We are really very close. I think my youngest *nga, ang mga ninong at ninang niya ay ang aming mga* school owners. And I am also the *ninang* of their children. *Parang* over the years, extended family *na kmi lahat*.
L#145-L#147

We are really very close. I think my youngest, his godparents are our school owners. And I am also the godmother of their children. Like, over the years, we have all become extended family.

This closeness was not limited to ceremonial occasions. Rather, it is embedded in the everyday rhythm of work. Crayon found motivation in the trust and camaraderie she experienced from the owning family each day. She utters:

The school treats us all like family. *Parang* we belong *na talaga*, we are very close, not only the employees but we are close to the owners, the family.

L#284-L#285

The school treats us all like family. Like we really belong, we are very close, not only the employees, but we are close to the owners, the family.

For Fastener, that sense of belonging became most visible during personal hardships with her family. The empathy of the institution and of the owning family was not just mere words, but tangible actions that supported her and solved her problems. She says:

Every time I encounter a problem in the family, the school is really supportive in helping me solve it.

L#98-L#103

The bonds extend well beyond the professional sphere, reinforced in moments of celebration and solidarity. Crayon recalls how this closeness is cemented by personal invitations that break the invisible wall often seen between owners and employees, where, instead of inviting other friends, the owning family chooses to celebrate their personal milestones with them. She explains:

In this school, if there are family celebrations of the owners, the guests are us, the employees.

L#288-L#289

Moments of solidarity in times of grief and hardship also define this belonging. Glue recounts how, when her mother died, the owners did not just send formal condolences, they took personal responsibility for ensuring she felt supported, reaching out to her regularly and extending help in many ways. Glue recalls:

When my mother died, the owners really called me from time to time and asked me how I was... They assured me that they will take care of everything. So I really value that much.

L#250-L#259

Even in the midst of internal tensions, the culture of belonging in the school is active and intentional. Eraser's approach to conflict reflects a commitment to the school's collective well-being. Even when navigating internal challenges, she frames her decisions through a lens of respect and care, where principles are sustained by this environment of belonging. She expounds:

They have conflicts on their own, internal conflicts. You just don't listen to them because you want to be comfy with the most powerful one, but you always listen, because you want to get the best decision for the school.
L#315-L#318

Notebook described his experience with a sense of calm fulfillment. He emphasized that envy or rivalry held no place in his perspective, as his role already gave him what mattered most: the capability to watch his kids everyday while performing his job. He shares:

I don't envy them, or I don't get jealous. I'm contented with my work, our set-up as a family. I can bring my kids to school. I can see my kids in school.
L#192-L#194

In this environment, belonging is not a passive inheritance but a living relationship that is built on continued, simple acts of care, and reinforced through years of trust, loyalty, and shared purpose. Belonging transforms the school from just a place where one earns into a second home, where professional and personal lives are woven together in ways that nurture familial relations and affirm that each member matters. Through these narratives, belonging reveals itself as something both intimate and enduring. It is felt in how the owners remember a spouse's name, in colleagues showing up for a funeral, in being invited to sit at the family table, and in the trust to speak honestly even when decisions are complex. This care is not episodic but it is sustained through small, consistent acts that affirm each person's place in the institution. In such a setting, the school becomes more than a workplace; it becomes a second home, where personal and professional lives are intertwined.

DISCUSSION

Guided by a narratological lens, the study revealed five narrative threads about the leadership narratives of middle administrators in second-generation family-owned schools: *emotional toll of fulfilling multiple roles as educators, leaders, and family members; leadership identity evolved through immersion, mentorship, and institutional loyalty; complexities of working in a family-owned institution where personal and professional spheres overlap; school's culture of faith and respect shaped their character and grounded their leadership; and, deep sense of belonging nurtured by a caring and supportive work environment.* These threads, while individually distinct, are interwoven, collectively providing insight into how middle leaders construct meaning, negotiate tensions, and sustain their leadership identities in the unique context of family-owned education.

First, the narratives revealed that middle administrators face emotional toll while simultaneously playing their multiple roles as teachers, administrators, and family

members. The studies of Cavanaugh et al. (2000) and Lipscombe et al. (2023) described this emotional toll as work-life strain that is characterized by exhaustion, role conflict, and difficulty balancing home life with professional duties. Nandiroh et al. (2023) further expounded that middle administrators in family-run institutions are faced with compounded pressures because the school owners, who are also the top-level administrators, all belong to the same family. This is echoed in the participants' accounts where they described how this work-life strain does not only happen once, but it is constantly woven into their daily lives. This constant weaving reflects the concept of Narrative Identity Theory by McAdams (1996) where people build their identity by linking their past and present experiences and their future aspirations into one coherent narrative. Furthermore, Cavanaugh et al. (2000) argued that workload, role conflict, and ambiguity result in work-related stress. This is visible in the participants' accounts where their role was not entirely professional, but also intimate and personal, with only the owning family making institutional decisions and leaving middle administrators with limited authority despite their significant leadership responsibilities. Moreover, work-life balance was repeatedly described by the participants as a challenge. Lipscombe et al. (2020) emphasized that middle administrators often perceive leadership as synonymous with longer hours and greater stress, an observation mirrored in participants' reflections about leadership as a burden carried into personal life. Participants narrated the strain of constantly negotiating across professional and generational hierarchies, from teachers and colleagues, to second-generation and first-generation family owners, echoing the study of Franken et al. (2015) which described middle leadership as inherently relational, requiring negotiation across vertical and horizontal organizational structures.

This narrative thread revealed that the burdens middle administrators face as they fulfill their multiple roles are not only limited to workload, but they involve emotional, relational, and value-based strains within the family-owned school context. As emphasized by Nandiroh et al. (2023), these burdens are made even more magnified because middle administrators not only have to meet institutional standards, but also the expectations of the owning family. However, although the emotional toll on the middle administrators revealed the weight of fulfilling multiple roles as educators, leaders, and family members, the same emotional toll also serves as the foundation from which their leadership identities were shaped and formed. Their daily work and home exhaustion, as well as the strain on their relationships, both professional and personal, became formative experiences that pushed them to rely on the mentorship of the founders and second-generation owners, the intimate culture of their family-owned institution, and their loyalty as lynchpin bridges within their unique organizational structure. From the emotional toll of personal, professional, and relational challenges, there evolved their leadership identities, forged not quickly in a snap, but in gradual, everyday balancing of multiple roles.

Second, the narratives reveal how immersion in school culture, mentorship from family owners, and long-term loyalty shaped the participants' leadership identity. The formation of the participants' leadership identity was not instantaneous but it evolved through time through an ongoing and enduring immersion in the daily life of the school. This was not a sudden transformation but a gradual process of being absorbed into the

rhythms, responsibilities, and culture of a family-owned institution, rooted in the legacy of the founders while transitioning to the innovations of the second-generation owners, echoing the study of Grootenboer et al. (2019) which found that middle leaders grow in their leadership roles through relational practice. Moreover, the participants recounted their journey from teachers to middle administrators and explained how each transition, though difficult, became a time of apprenticeship that expanded their understanding of the institution. This aligns with the study of Lipscombe et al. (2023), which characterized the leadership of middle administrators as ambiguous yet highly influential, necessitating contextual learning or learning on the job. This also aligns with the study of De Nobile (2024) that middle administrators require intentional leadership preparation, since many are promoted on teaching ability rather than leadership capacity. Equally formative was the mentorship they received from the founders and later from the second-generation owners. Participants recalled how the first-generation founders modeled leadership that was personal, value-driven, and deeply relational. Correction was offered with care, guidance was provided directly, and expectations were framed in ways that emphasized patience and growth, in accordance to the school's vision and mission. This mentoring culture was later mirrored in the way the participants themselves engaged with their own subordinates. The transition to the second generation of owners introduced new expectations, but the culture of guidance and personal care remained an important anchor, reinforcing leadership practices rooted in empathy and relational sensitivity. This echoed Harris and Jones (2017) and Sothinathan et al. (2024), who stress the importance of mentorship and professional development in middle leadership.

Participants shared how a strong sense of loyalty has developed over years of immersion and mentorship with many describing their loyalty as reinforced by the trust extended to them in leadership responsibilities and by the relationships built across generations of ownership. Loyalty, therefore, was not just expressed in longevity of service but in an enduring identification with the mission and legacy of the institution, echoing research that highlights loyalty as a stabilizing force in multigenerational family-owned schools. These findings align with Sorensen and Ladd (2020), who emphasized that loyalty mitigates institutional disruptions, and with Sharma and Irving (2005), who argued that continuity of values across generations strengthens organizational identity and commitment. In this narrative thread, immersion, mentorship, and loyalty together illustrate how middle administrators' leadership identities are shaped gradually through lived experience.

Third, the participants' accounts revealed the unique complexities of leading in a family-owned educational enterprise. Unlike other schools, where hierarchies are more formal, family-run institutions often experience overlaps in between professional authority and familial relationships. Participants described the difficulty of leading in a family institution where personal and professional are deeply intertwined, mirroring the studies of Martin-Santana et al. (2020) and Nandiroh et al. (2023) that familiness can limit autonomy. A central complexity raised by participants was the limitation of authority despite bearing significant responsibility. Administrators described the tension of managing teachers, programs, and operations while lacking the autonomy to make final decisions. This echoed Bush's (2018) definition of middle leadership as a dilemma of high

responsibility paired with limited authority. The tension of bearing responsibility without the freedom to decide underscored a recurring challenge in their leadership, revealing how structural constraints in family-owned schools can erode both efficiency and confidence in middle-level leadership. Alongside these constraints, familial relations added another layer of challenge. Participants noted that in moments of conflict, family ties often outweighed professional competence, tilting outcomes in favor of kinship. This mirrors Steffens et al. (2014) and Tabor et al. (2017), who emphasize the role of non-family leaders as mediators, bridging family and organizational needs. Participants' experiences confirm these insights, showing how middle administrators, particularly non-family members, often carried the responsibility of bridging the gaps between owners and front-line teachers while maintaining professional obligations. These dynamics were further compounded by relational conflicts that made leadership even more ambiguous. Further, the middle administrators also found themselves caught between honoring the legacy and tradition established by the founders while also adapting to modern educational demands. This echoes Harris and Jones (2017) who describe ambiguity in middle leadership as even more magnified by loyalty and legacy pressures in family-owned institutions. The studies of Grubman and Jaffe (2010) and Macasinag (2019) similarly emphasize that second-generation institutions demand a careful balance of heritage and innovation, while Sukamdani (2023) shows that schools across Southeast Asia, likewise, face parallel struggles in reconciling familial traditions with professional obligations.

Fourth, the study revealed that the participants' willingness to remain in leadership depended on alignment with the school values of faith and respect. Participants also recognized the reality of tensions in their interactions with the multi-generational owners, reflecting the study Othman et al. (2024) that generational differences within school owners can create value mismatches. Faith and respect emerged as anchors in participants' narratives, shaping both their character and their leadership. The middle administrators consistently described the school's Christ-centered mission as a moral compass in decision-making and interactions. This is consistent with the study of Shields (2017) which defined transformative leadership as rooted in justice and equity, extending moral responsibility and transformative leadership in schools where professional and personal values are interwoven, leading middle administrators to draw upon faith and respect as leadership anchors over just personal convictions. Furthermore, Nguyen (2021) argues that faith-informed leadership offers moral grounding and highlights how moral clarity and resilience contribute towards successful navigation of complexities inherent in family-owned institutions. This was evident in the participants' description of their constant reliance on faith values and grounding at times of ambiguity and tension, reflecting how faith values shape character and ground leadership.

Lastly, the study revealed that participants narrated a strong sense of belonging within their schools, often describing them as extended families. This sense of belonging was shaped over years of trust, care, and collaboration instead of being an abstract concept, where participants saw themselves as integral to their institutions, mirroring Martín-Santana et al. (2024) that familiness is a relational social capital where stronger commitment to the family-owned institution is fostered through trust building. Local

studies, such as that of Legaspi and Fernandez (2022) confirmed that a sense of belonging and shared purpose influences commitment in Philippine private schools, while Amoguis (2024) found that intimate relational dynamics are rooted in belongingness and trust. With the narratives of the middle administrators, it was evident that belongingness was deeply rooted in a shared identity. This shows that belonging functions as a vital counterweight that stabilizes the emotional toll of middle leadership. It anchors administrators in communities of care, reinforces their purpose, and sustains their motivation even amidst challenges.

Taken together, these narrative threads are not isolated but interconnected dimensions of leadership in second-generation family-owned schools where the emotional tolls of fulfilling multiple roles birthed leadership identities that are shaped and formed within the complexities of personal and professional, shaped in faith and respect and grounded in a deep sense of belongingness. Woven together, these threads illustrate that the leadership of middle administrators in the context of the school they serve is not only positional but deeply narrative – *where each story is a story of leadership, loyalty, identity, and institutional legacy.*

Conclusions

This study revealed that middle administrators in second-generation family-owned schools construct their leadership identities through the continuous negotiation of overlapping personal, professional, and relational roles while facing the emotional toll of balancing teaching, administrative, and family responsibilities, compounded by limited authority yet high accountability. Despite these tensions, their leadership identities were formed through immersion in school culture, mentorship from founders and senior colleagues, and long-term institutional loyalty. Participants highlighted the unique complexities of working in family-owned institutions requiring them to mediate between owners, teachers, and colleagues while honoring tradition and adapting to change. Faith and respect consistently anchored their leadership, serving as moral compasses in times of ambiguity, while a deep sense of belonging within the school community sustained their commitment and resilience.

Recommendations

The findings of this study shed light on the leadership narratives of middle administrators in second-generation family-owned schools, with implications extending across various aspects of educational practice. For family-owned schools, these results highlight the need to meticulously design and implement systematic support mechanisms for middle administrators who carry the weight of multiple roles, often with limited authority. Equally important is the establishment of standardized promotion guidelines and policies for potential and current middle administrators. Family-owned institutions can benefit from establishing transparent, merit-based developmental promotion processes that integrate technical skills and credentials with school-based criteria such as tenure and values alignment. Beyond the individual institution, the findings offer valuable insights for educational policymakers, accrediting bodies, and associations that oversee private schools. Recognizing the distinct dynamics of family-owned institutions, these bodies can

craft leadership standards, training modules, and policy recommendations tailored to the unique challenges of schools where personal and professional spheres intersect.

Future researchers may expand the scope to include other school stakeholders, such as the founders, the second-generation owners, and the teachers and staff who work alongside the middle administrators to provide a variety of perspectives into the narratives. Doing so can help illuminate how the co-construction of leadership across different voices and not solely from the stories of the middle administrators. Moreover, future researchers may explore broader cultural contexts of family-owned institutions in other parts of the Philippines and even in Southeast Asia, where there is a strong societal presence of family, faith, and education. Doing so can better highlight how culture and religion shape leadership narratives, and open a larger discourse on the shared and the unique narratives of middle leaders across these locations. Finally, since the model used in the research is limited only to commonalities across narratives, future researchers may explore other frameworks that can capture commonalities, divergences, and contradictions to have a more nuanced understanding of how middle administrators in family-owned schools construct and navigate their leadership identities.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Throughout the conduct of the study, the researcher remained committed to upholding and respecting the ethical standards in research of the University of the Immaculate Conception Graduate School by submitting the study to the Research Ethics Committee for review and approval to ensure that the participants' rights, dignity, and privacy were properly respected. The participants voluntarily participated in the study. The researcher strictly adhered to standard ethical principles, including informed consent, confidentiality, and data privacy mandated by the policies and standards of the University of Immaculate Conception.

Acknowledgments

The researcher thanks the participants for their trust in sharing their narratives, the University of the Immaculate Conception for the privilege to conduct her research, and all Filipino middle administrators who are working tirelessly to bridge the gap between owners and teachers.

REFERENCES

- Amoguis, J. A. (2024). Surviving the Dynamic Business Landscape: The Influence of Dynamic Capabilities on Organizational Resilience. 11th International Scholars Conference, 11(3), 681-698. Retrieved from <https://jurnal.unai.edu/index.php/isc/article/view/3401>
- Bassett, Martin & Shaw, Nicholas. (2018). Building the confidence of first time middle leaders in New Zealand primary schools. *International Journal of Educational Management*. 32. 00-00. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-05-2017-0101>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>

- Bush, T. (2018). Transformational leadership: Exploring common conceptions. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 46(6), 883–887. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1741143218795731>
- Cavanaugh, M. A., Boswell, W. R., Roehling, M. V., & Boudreau, J. W. (2000). An empirical examination of self-reported work stress among U.S. managers. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 85(1), 65–74. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.85.1.65>
- Clandinin, D.J. & Connelly, F.M. (2000). *Narrative Inquiry: Experience and story in qualitative research*. Jossey-Bass.
- Creswell, J. W., & Poth, C. N. (2018). *Qualitative inquiry: Research design, collecting and analyzing data* (5th ed.). Sage Publications.
- De Massis, A., Kotlar, J., & Manelli, L. (2021). Family firms, family boundary organizations, and the family-related organizational ecosystem. *Family Business Review*, 34(1), 6–27. <https://doi.org/10.1177/08944865211052195>
- De Nobile, J. (2018). Towards a theoretical model of middle leadership in schools. *School Leadership & Management*, 38(4), 395–416. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13632434.2017.1411902>
- Dutta, Tanusree & Dhir, Swati. (2021). Employee Loyalty: Measurement and Validation. *Global Business Review*. 26. 097215092199080. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0972150921990809>
- Franken, M., Penney, D., & Branson, C. (2015). Middle leaders' learning in a university context. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 37(2), 190–203. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1360080X.2015.1019120>
- Grootenboer, P., Edwards-Groves, C., & Rönnerman, K. (2019). Understanding middle leadership: Practices and policies. *School Leadership & Management*, 39(3–4), 251–254. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13632434.2019.1611712>
- Grubman, J., & Jaffe, D.T. (2010). Client Relationships and Family Dynamics: Competencies and Services Necessary for Truly Integrated Wealth Management. *The Journal of Wealth Management*, 13, 16 - 31.
- Hargreaves, Andy & Shirley, Dennis. (2019). Leading from the middle: its nature, origins and importance. *Journal of Professional Capital and Community*. Ahead-of-print. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JPCC-06-2019-0013>
- Harris, A., Jones, M., Ismail, N., & Nguyen, D. (2019). Middle leaders and middle leadership in schools: Exploring the knowledge base (2003–2017). *School Leadership & Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13632434.2019.1578738>
- Harris, A., & Jones, M. (2017). Middle leaders matter: Reflections, recognition, and renaissance. *School Leadership & Management*, 37(3), 213–216. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13632434.2017.1323339>
- Hyslop, K., Ingram, A., & Hughes, M. (2023). Managing the tensions between tradition and innovation in family firms. *Journal of Family Business Management*, 13(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFBM-09-2024-0213>
- Knight, S. D. (2009). The power of students' stories: Narrative inquiry in English education. *Journal of Language and Literacy Education*, 5(1), 48–58.
- Legaspi, J. A., & Fernandez, E. J. (2022). Motivation to longevity of mid-career private school teachers amidst turnover. In *South Florida Journal of Development* (Vol. 3, Issue 6, p. 6347). <https://doi.org/10.46932/sfjdv3n6-002>
- Lipscombe, K., Grice, C., Tindall-Ford, S., & De-Nobile, J. (2020). Middle leading in Australian schools: professional standards, positions, and professional development. *School Leadership & Management*, 40(5), 406–424. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13632434.2020.1731685>
- Lipscombe, K., Tindall-Ford, S., & Lamanna, J. (2023). School middle leadership: A

- systematic review. *Educational Management, Administration & Leadership*, 51(2), 270–288. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17411432211044980>
- Macasinag, M. L. (2019). Decades of Educational Excellence: A case study of a successful Family-Owned Higher Educational Institution. *JPAIR Institutional Research*, 13(1), 63–84. <https://doi.org/10.7719/irj.v13i1.783>
- Martín-Santana, Josefa & Cabrera-Suárez, M. Katuska & Déniz-Déniz, M^a. (2020). Familiness, social capital and market orientation in the family firm. *European Journal of Marketing*. ahead-of-print. <https://10.1108/EJM-04-2018-0274>.
- Merriam, S. B., & Tisdell, E. J. (2016). *Qualitative research: A guide to design and implementation* (4th ed.). Jossey-Bass. <https://10.1108/EJM-04-2018-0274>
- Nandiroh, Umi & Sudarmiatin, Sudarmiatin & Hermawan, Agus. (2023). Leadership Styles and Financial management of Family Businesses : Case Studies. *International Journal Of Humanities Education and Social Sciences (IJHESS)*. 2. <https://10.55227/ijhess.v2i6.493>.
- National Association of Secondary School Principals. (2022, September 6). NASSP survey of principals and students reveals the extent of challenges facing schools. NASSP. Retrieved from <https://www.nassp.org/2022/09/06/nassp-survey-of-principals-and-students-reveals-the-extent-of-challenges-facing-schools/>
- Nguyen, Linda (2021). "Social Justice Leadership in Catholic Secondary Schools: A Critical Examination of Social Justice Orientation and Praxis". *LMU Theses And Dissertations*. 996. <https://digitalcommons.lmu.edu/etd/996>
- Nixon, E. (2023). Middle leaders in schools least happy. *Education Review*. Retrieved from <https://www.educationreview.com.au/2023/08/middle-leaders-in-schools-least-happy/>
- Othman, A. K., Othman, N., Wan Rashid, W. E., Saihani, S. B., Zainal Abidin, Z., Abdul Rashid, M. A., A Rahman, M. K., & Abdul Kadir, M. A. B. (2024). The mismatch between individual values and organizational values among different generations in the workplace. *Information Management and Business Review*, 16(3(I)S), 211–218. [https://doi.org/10.22610/imbr.v16i3\(I\)S.4026](https://doi.org/10.22610/imbr.v16i3(I)S.4026)
- Perez, R. P. (2021). Attributes of middle-level managers in the Philippines higher education institutions. *IOER International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5520367>
- Ramos, Bethel & Malangen, Ardrian. (2023). The Level of Effectivity of Micromanagement Among the Teachers and Middle Managers in the Basic Education. 8. 648-658. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7890089>
- Riessman, C. K. (2008). *Narrative methods for the human sciences*. Sage Publications, Inc.
- Sharma, P., & Irving, P. G. (2005). Four bases of family business successor commitment: Antecedents and consequences. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 29(1), 13–33. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6520.2005.00067.x>
- Shields, C.M. (2017). *Transformative Leadership in Education: Equitable and Socially Just Change in an Uncertain and Complex World* (2nd ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315207148>
- Sihombing, Sabrina & Berlianto, Margaretha. (2017). Antecedents of Employee Loyalty in Educational Setting: An Empirical Study. *International Research Journal of Business Studies*. 10. 99-109. <https://doi.org/10.21632/irjbs.10.2.99-109>
- Sothinathan, J. S., Adams, D., & Mohd Radzi, N. (2024). From leadership to allegiance: The interplay of middle leadership, teacher job satisfaction and commitment in schools. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 38(5), 1342-1356. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-01-2024-0057>
- Sorensen, L. & Ladd, H. (2020). The hidden costs of teacher turnover. *AERA Open*.

- 6(1), 1-24. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/2332858420905812>
- Steffens, N. K., Haslam, S. A., Reicher, S. D., Platow, M. J., Fransen, K., Yang, J., Ryan, M. K., Jetten, J., Peters, K., & Boen, F. (2014). Leadership as social identity management: Introducing the Identity Leadership Inventory (ILI) to assess and validate a four-dimensional model. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 25(5), 1001–1024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2014.05.002>
- Sukamdani, Nugroho. (2023). Family business dynamics in Southeast Asia: A comparative study of Indonesia, Malaysia, Singapore, and Thailand. *JAS (Journal of ASEAN Studies)*. <https://doi.org/10.21512/jas.v11i1.9518>
- Tabor, W., Chrisman, J. J., Madison, K., & Vardaman, J. M. (2017). Nonfamily Members in Family Firms: A Review and Future Research Agenda. *Family Business Review*, 31(1), 54-79. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0894486517734683>
- Upadhyaya, A., & Kuknor, S. (2025). Challenges faced by family-owned education institutions in Nepal in implementing effective succession planning strategies. *Journal of Applied Research in Higher Education*, 17(1), 175–189. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JARHE-04-2023-0151>
- Wertz, Frederick & Charmaz, Kathy & McMullen, L.M. & Josselson, Ruthellen & Anderson, R. & McSpadden, Emalinda. (2011). *Five Ways of Doing Qualitative Analysis: Phenomenological Psychology, Grounded Theory, Discourse Analysis, Narrative Research, and Intuitive Inquiry*.